

Von Zugang zur Überwachung

neue Geschäftsmodelle der alten Verlage

Prof. Dr. Björn Brembs, Universität Regensburg

Prof. Dr. Konrad Förstner, ZB MED - Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften & TH Köln

Open Access Week 2022, 26. Oktober, 2022

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7252825> / <https://doi.org/jh7t>

Stop Tracking Science

The major academic publishers have made collection and trading of data about the research interests of individuals, groups and research institutions their new business model. Data about your scientific activities are collected in real time across the research workflow. The publishers take notes and sell the knowledge about you to third parties. This business model is in direct opposition to academic freedom. We have to stand up against these corporations!

Stop Tracking Science!

A fundamental transformation is currently changing scholarly publishing to the detriment of science and society. After the commercialization and ensuing development of a dominant oligopoly of a few major

Datentracking in der Wissenschaft: Aggregation und Verwendung bzw. Verkauf von Nutzungsdaten durch Wissenschaftsverlage

Ein Informationspapier des Ausschusses
für Wissenschaftliche Bibliotheken und Informationssysteme
der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft
18. Juni 2021

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Das Lesen der Anderen

Die Auswirkungen von User Tracking auf Bibliotheken

Renke Siems

Universitätsbibliothek Tübingen

<http://orcid.org/0000-0002-9824-5449>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/5797>

Schlagwörter: Wissenschaftliches Publizieren, Überwachungskapitalismus

Abstract

Die großen Wissenschaftsverlage entwickelten sich in den vergangenen Jahren weg von einem verlegerischen Inhaltsanbieter hin zu einem Data Analytics Business. Als Plattformunternehmen er zielen sie hohe Margen und nutzen dieses Kapital, um aus der Wissenschaftscommunity entstehende Alternativangebote aufzukaufen und sich in weitere Geschäftsfelder

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contributing processes. We found that these processes explain the observed twentieth-century GMSL trend and match the multidecadal variability pattern, except for the low rates in observed sea-level rise during the 1920s. Barystatic changes are the primary contributors to sea-level rise, with glacier mass loss being the largest component. The sea-level rise during the 1970s. The relative contributions of the thermohaline barystatic changes to GMSL vary with time. On basin scales, trends in multidecadal variability deviate from the global mean, mostly due to local variability in the steric component.

In the subpolar North Atlantic, along which almost half of all tide gauges used in this study are located, including many of the longest available records, the ocean-mass contribution over the twentieth century is negligible, whereas GIA causes relative sea level to rise in this basin. This combination results in sea-level trends that are comparable to global-mean trends, but caused by a different combination of processes. Although many of the world's longest tide-gauge records, including the 225-year record from Amsterdam and the 220-year record from Brest, are located along the coast of the subpolar North Atlantic, long-term changes derived from these records are not representative of global-mean

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The causes of sea-level rise since 1900

We reconstructed the GMSL since 1900 and compared it to the sum of the contributing processes. We found that these processes explain the observed twentieth-century GMSL trend and match the multidecadal variability pattern, except for the low rates in observed sea-level rise during the 1920s. Barystatic changes are the primary contributor to sea-level rise, with glacier mass loss being the largest component. Reservoir impoundment caused a substantial, albeit temporary, slowdown of GMSL rise during the 1970s. The relative contributions of thermosteric and barystatic changes to GMSL vary with time. On basin scales, trends and multidecadal variability deviate from the global mean, mostly as a result of variability in the steric component.

In the subpolar North Atlantic, along which almost half of all tide gauges used in this study are located, including many of the longest available records, the ocean-mass contribution over the twentieth century is negligible, whereas GIA causes relative sea level to rise in this basin. This combination results in sea-level trends that are comparable to global-mean trends, but caused by a different combination of processes. Although many of the world's longest tide-gauge records, including the 225-year record from Amsterdam and the 220-year record from Brest, are located along the coast of the subpolar North Atlantic, long-term changes derived from these records are not representative of global-mean changes.

Closure of the twentieth-century sea-level budget, as demonstrated here, implies that no additional unknown processes, such as large-scale deep-ocean thermal expansion or additional mass loss from the Antarctic Ice Sheet, are required to explain the observed changes in global sea level. Such additional processes had been speculated to explain the non-closure found in previous studies of global sea-level budget^{2,3,12}. Our demonstration of closure of the global-mean and basin-mean sea-level budget forms a consistent baseline

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Wie werden Daten getrackt?

- Einbau von Third-Party Assets
- Browser Fingerprinting
- Audience Tools
- Port Scanning
- Aggregated Identity

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 Access through your institution

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Abstract

Urgent challenges posed by widespread degradation in tropical ecosystems with poor governance require new development pathways to reconcile biodiversity, conservation and human welfare. Community-

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SCIENCEINSIDER | SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY

Move by journals to 'seamless' off-campus access raises privacy concerns

Other journals eyeing service debuted this week by Nature

15 NOV 2019 • BY [JEFFREY BRAINARD](#)

<https://www.science.org/news/2019/11/move-journals-seamless-campus-access-raises-privacy-concerns>

AUTHORITARIAN TECH

GOGI KAMUSHADZE

Proposal to install spyware in university libraries to protect copyrights shocks academics

The hypothetical plan to combat digital piracy called for the use of software to monitor those accessing academic material

BY GAUTAMA MEHTA 13 NOVEMBER, 2020 BRIEF

<https://www.codastory.com/authoritarian-tech/spyware-in-libraries/>

Scholarly Networks Security Initiative (SNSI): working together to combat the threat of cybercrime

Cybercrime is a huge threat to the entire scholarly ecosystem and safeguarding data and privacy is paramount. Higher education institutions need protection from cyber-attacks. Their data and their users' data must be protected.

Researchers need confidence that research they are using is correct, up to date and properly connected to the scientific record.

Cybersecurity isn't just an issue for publishers. It isn't just a challenge for librarians. It is not just an obstacle for institutions or nuisance for researchers. This is an issue for all of us, and a problem that we firmly believe can be best addressed sustainably and effectively together.

Was kann mit den Daten gemacht werden?

“Data is the new oil”

(Clive Humby)

The Intercept_

Photo illustration: Soohee Cho/The Intercept, DVIDS

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LEXISNEXIS TO PROVIDE GIANT DATABASE OF PERSONAL INFORMATION TO ICE

The company signed a contract with an ICE division that plays a key role in deportations.

Sam Biddle
April 2 2021, 4:00 p.m.

THE POPULAR LEGAL RESEARCH and data brokerage firm LexisNexis signed a \$16.8 million contract to sell information to U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement, according to documents shared with The Intercept.

<https://theintercept.com/2021/04/02/ice-database-surveillance-lexisnexis/>

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Science Tracking in den letzten Jahren

Brazil, Gilliam, 1985

- Wandel der Verlage vom Content-Provider zur Data-Broker
- Teil eines entfesselten Überwachungskapitalismus
- Verknüpfung von Aktivitäten bei Arbeits- und Privatleben
- Fehleranfälligkeit des Systems - Gefahr der Fehlklassifikation
- Freiheit von Forschung und Lehre ist gefährdet
- Bibliotheken in der Rolle der Steigbügelhalter für diese Data-Broker

October 24 - 30, 2022

Open for Climate Justice

Open Access Week 2022

Open Access Week 2022 is an opportunity to join together, take action, and raise awareness around how open can be a means for climate justice.

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<https://www.openaccessweek.org/>

Climate crimes
Climate science

This article is more than 7 months old

Revealed: leading climate research publisher helps fuel oil and gas drilling

Elsevier's work with fossil fuel companies 'drags us towards disaster', climate researcher says

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About this content

Amy Westervelt

@amywestervelt

Thu 24 Feb 2022 08.00 GMT

Elsevier is one of a few companies that publish peer-reviewed climate research, but it also consults with industry to find oil and gas reserves. Photograph: Kristoffer Trippelaar/Alamy

Scientists working with one of the world's largest climate research publishers say they're increasingly alarmed that the company works with the fossil fuel industry to help increase oil and gas drilling, the Guardian can reveal.

Wie passt Tracking in das Big Picture?

Europäische Kommission: “Verlage sind Monopolisten”

*Case No COMP/M.3197 -
CANDOVER / CINVEN /
BERTELSMANN-
SPRINGER*

Only the English text is available and authentic.

**REGULATION (EEC) No 4064/89
MERGER PROCEDURE**

Article 6(2) NON-OPPOSITION
Date: 29/07/2003

13. In line with a previous Commission’s decision², a strict demand approach to define a market for publications is not appropriate. From a demand-side point of view, it is rare that two different publications be viewed as perfect substitutes. There usually are differences in the coverage, comprehensiveness and content provided by two different publications. From the point of view of functional interchangeability, two different publications could hardly be regarded as substitutable by the end-users, the readers. This

Therefore, Consumers will rarely substitute one publication for another in reaction to their relative prices. In this case, a strict demand approach would lead to the definition of a multitude of relevant markets of imprecise boundaries and small dimensions. This

Verhandlungen mit Monopolisten

WER NUR MIT EINEM BIETER VERHANDELT, MUSS SICHER SEIN, DASS DESSEN PRODUKT KONKURRENZLOS IST

Ein Auftraggeber darf ein Verhandlungsverfahren ohne Teilnahmewettbewerb mit nur einem Bieter nur dann durchführen, wenn er darlegen kann, dass kein anderes Unternehmen in der EU in der Lage ist, die zu beschaffende Leistung zu erbringen.

Der Anbieter müsse praktisch Monopolist für die nachgefragte Leistung sein. Nur soweit dieser Nachweis gelingt, ist ein Wettbewerb um den öffentlichen Auftrag tatsächlich unmöglich und die Durchführung eines wettbewerblichen Vergabeverfahrens obsolet.

Falls es dagegen Alternativen gibt, besteht kein Ausschließlichkeitsrecht, das den Verzicht auf ein wettbewerbliches Vergabeverfahren rechtfertigt. ■

Wie passt Tracking in das Big Picture?

Wie passt Tracking in das Big Picture?

[10.12688/f1000research.27468.2](https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.27468.2)

Wohin mit dem Geld?

Elsevier Mergers and Acquisitions

Wohin mit dem Geld?

Wiley Mergers and Acquisitions

Wie passt Tracking in das Big Picture?

Seit ca. ~2012

Kopernio

Monopole ausbauen

Digitale Souveränität

Kein Outsourcing von kritischen Infrastrukturen mehr!

Make it required

Make it rewarding

Make it normative

Make it easy

Make it possible

September 24, 2021

Journal article Open Access

Replacing academic journals

 Sara Rodriguez-Cuadrado

A major factor underlying several of scholarship's most pressing problems is its antiquated journal system with its trifecta of reproducibility, affordability and functionality crises. Any solution needs to not only solve the current problems but also be capable of preventing a takeover by corporations. Technically, there is broad agreement on the goal for a modern scholarly digital infrastructure: it needs to replace traditional journals with a decentralized, resilient, evolvable network that is interconnected by open standards under the governance of the scholarly community. It needs to replace the monopolies of current journals with a genuine, functioning and well-regulated market. In this new market, substitutable service providers compete and innovate according to the conditions of the scholarly community, avoiding further vendor lock-in. Redirection of funding from the legacy publishers to the new framework may be realized by a tried-and-tested incentive system: Funding agencies have ensured minimum standards at funded institutions by requiring specific infrastructures. These requirements, updated to include the new framework, provide exquisite incentives for institutions to redirect their infrastructure funds from antiquated journals to modern technology. At the same time and enabled by this plan, new, modern and adaptable reputation systems, long demanded by the scientific community, can finally be implemented.

Ownership involves socially recognized economic rights, first and foremost the exclusive control over that property, with the self-efficacy it affords. The inability to exert such control over crucial components of their scholarly infrastructure in the face of a generally recognized need for action for over three decades now, evinces the dramatic erosion of real ownership rights for the scholarly community over said infrastructure. Thus, this proposal is motivated not only by the now very urgent need to restore such ownership to the scholarly community, but also by the understanding that through their funding bodies, scholars may have an effective and proven avenue at their disposal to identify game-changing actions and to design a financial incentive structure for recipient institutions

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Plan I, infrastructure, journals, scholarship, literature, research data, source code, science

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Anreize zur digitalen Souveränität setzen I

Wissenschaftsrat, 2022:

kationsorgane getroffen werden. Dies ist eine Voraussetzung dafür, Publikationsmöglichkeiten substituierbar zu machen und so einen Wettbewerb zwischen Anbietern von Publikationsdienstleistungen zu ermöglichen. Zugleich

Anreize zur digitalen Souveränität setzen I

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NEWS | 24 April 2019 | Brussels, Belgium | Research and Innovation

The EC to launch a new a tender for an open access publishing platform

The European Commission is committed to supporting beneficiaries in complying with open access requirements in Horizon 2020, as well as supporting open access publishing as the main mode of publishing research in the context of open science. To this end, the EC will soon launch a tender for an open access publishing platform, subsequent to a tendering procedure which led to a non-award in 2018. The intended result is an open access publishing platform where peer-reviewed articles and related pre-prints produced with the financial support of Horizon 2020 can be published efficiently and under high standards of quality.

Anreize zur digitalen Souveränität setzen I

2022 Council Conclusions on Open Science

“21. WELCOMES the setting up of Open Research Europe, the open access publishing platform established by the Commission, as well as similar platforms and open access university presses established by both public and private research funders within the European Union and beyond, as well as dedicated research infrastructures such as OpenAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe) and OPERAS (Open scholarly communication in the European Research Area for social sciences and humanities); **INVITES Members States and research funding organisations to consider joining the Open Research Europe initiative** in order to improve its quality and attractiveness **or, if this is not possible, to consider setting up their own open access publishing platforms, if necessary;**”

Anreize zur digitalen Souveränität setzen I

A vision for ORE beyond 2026

- A top-quality, trusted **pan-European OA publishing service**
- **Collectively driven, owned and supported** by European research funders and research institutions, as a service for **researchers**, with **no author-facing fees**
- Supported by an **open source infrastructure**
- **Ambition for a Diamond OA** publishing service

Publikationsdienstleistungen
müssen
ausgeschrieben
werden!

Anreize zur digitalen Souveränität setzen II

cOAlition S members and their policies

Which of these funding agencies have specific eligibility criteria in place for institutions to receive funding? For instance, these can be infrastructure requirements, requirements to support good scientific practice or accreditation requirements.

Name	country	Eligibility criteria (Y/N)?	Policy link(s)
SAMRC	ZA	?	
FWF	AT	Y	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.fwf.ac.at/fileadmin/files/Dokumente/Ueber_den_FWF/Publikationen/EFW-relevante_Publikationen/fwf_foerderungsrichtlinien.pdf https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/decision-making-procedure-evaluation/funding-guidelines/eligibility-to-apply-application-requirements
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INFN	IT	?	
FNR	LU	Y	https://www.fnr.lu/fnr-beneficiaries
NWO	NL	Y	https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/NWO%20Grant%20rules%202017%20-%20version%20January%202019%20-%20EN.pdf
FR	NO	Y	https://www.forskingsradet.no/sok-om-finansiering/hve-m-kan-soke-om-finansiering/forskingsorganisasjoner/godkjente-forskingsorganisasjoner
NSC	PL	?	https://ncn.gov.pl/finansowanie-nauki/pomoc-publiczna?language=en
SRA	SI	?	
Forte	SE	Y	https://forte.se/sok-finansiering/att-soka-bidrag/vem-kan

			-soka
Formas	SE	Y	https://www.formas.se/soka-finansiering/sa-har-gar-det-till/vem-kan-soka-finansiering/vem-kan-bli-medelsforvaltare.html
UKRI	UK	Y	https://www.ukri.org/apply-for-funding/before-you-apply/check-if-you-are-eligible-for-research-and-innovation-funding/apply-to-become-an-eligible-organisation/#contents-list
NSTC	ZM	Y	https://nstc.org.zm/index.php/registration
HCST	JO	?	
Vinnova	SE	Y	Different in each call
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https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uG1mcOEKLFaJm9PDvink_Tabjzsb4alnf4pw7LJOg/edit?usp=sharing

Publikationsinfrastruktur
für Texte, Daten und
Code/Software/Modelle
muss Grundausstattung sein!

Fazit

- Publikationsdienstleistungen müssen ausgeschrieben werden
- Publikationsinfrastrukturen für Texte, Daten und Code/Software/Modelle müssen Grundausstattung sein
- Nutzer*Innen werden Souverän ihrer Daten (auch Workflow-Tools!)

Dank an

- Renke Siems
- Gerhard Lauer
- Claudia Müller-Birn
- Felix Schönbrodt
- Peter Kraker
- Petra Labriga

Danke für die Aufmerksamkeit - wie lauten Ihre Fragen?